

Hydrolysis of α and β Naphthyl Phosphates

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Hydrolysis of α and β naphthyl phosphates has been found to be acid catalysed and proceeds both via conjugate acid and neutral species. A rate maxima at 7 M perchloric acid has been observed and rates then decrease. Experimental rates have been confirmed by those determined from ionic strength data and sum of acid and neutral rates agrees well upto 5 M perchloric acid. Detailed kinetic study using concepts such as Arrhenius and Bunnett parameters, solvent effect and solvent isotope effect show that conjugate acid species of substrate involves a nucleophilic attack of water molecule.

ARYL phosphates with *p*-substituted electron attracting groups as chloro, bromo and nitro have been found to show acid catalysis and the order effectiveness of acid catalysis follows the order $\text{NO}_2 > \text{CH}_3\text{CO} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br}$. The behaviour inexplicable on the basis of polar effects has been interpreted as involving electrolytic effects of special nature^{1,2}.

Hydrolysis of α and β naphthyl phosphates has been studied with a view to know the behaviour of substituted naphthyl rings towards acid catalysis, assuming one side ring to be equivalent to *p*-substituted group in *p*-substituted aryl phosphates. A mechanism which satisfies the experimental observations has been proposed for the hydrolysis.

Experimental

α and β naphthyl phosphates were prepared from α and β naphthol, phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine. The resulting α and β naphthyl phosphorodichloridate was hydrolyzed and recrystallized several times from benzene-acetone and chloroform-acetone mixtures respectively^{3,4}.

α -naphthyl phosphate : m.p. 157°; reported 157°–158°.

β -naphthyl phosphate : m.p. 177°; reported 177°–178°.

Procedure

The hydrolysis of α and β naphthyl phosphates ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) was followed by colorimetric estimations of inorganic phosphate by Allen's method⁵ at 80°. Good first order rate constants were obtained. The constant ionic strengths were maintained using mixtures of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate^{2,6}.

Dioxan was purified by standard method⁷. Deuterium oxide of isotopic purity > 99.4% was procured from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay.

Results and Discussion

Hydrolysis of α and β naphthyl phosphates has been investigated in the range pH 0 to 8M perchloric acid. The rates have been found to increase upto 7M perchloric acid as in other *p*-halogeno² and *p*-nitro phenyl phosphates; and then rates decrease. The results are summarized in Table 1. The decrease

TABLE 1—RATES OF HYDROLYSIS OF α AND β -NAPHTHYL PHOSPHATES AT 80°

HClO ₄ (M)	<i>k</i> , min. ⁻¹		<i>k</i> , min. ⁻¹	
	α -naphthyl phosphate ($\times 10^3$)		β -naphthyl phosphate ($\times 10^3$)	
	Observed	Calculated	Observed	Calculated
1.0	+0.6440 0.2993	0.5019	0.3995 0.3065	0.2811
2.0	0.6771	0.6441	0.4832	0.3818
3.0	+0.7320 0.3293	0.7064	0.5363	0.4713
4.0	++0.8219 0.579	0.7769	0.6406	0.6157
5.0	+0.8900 0.3263	0.9073	+0.8160 0.4103	0.8666
6.0	—	1.13	0.8344	1.309
7.0	1.0000	1.506	+0.8408 0.4335	2.041
8.0	0.4661	—	0.4611	—

+ Dioxan-water. α -naphthyl phosphate—
A = 4.92×10^{12} sec.⁻¹
++ Deuterium oxide. β -naphthyl phosphate—
A = 2.06×10^4 sec.⁻¹
 $\Delta S^\ddagger = -41.08$ e.u.

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of rates after 7M perchloric acid is not expected to be due to maximum protonation as in amide systems since esters are not as basic as amides⁸. Acid catalysis is not expected since rise of rates with increase in acid concentration is very slow. This increase in acid concentration may also be due to ionic acceleration. In order to investigate the cause of increase of rates ionic strength effect has been studied in perchloric acid⁶. The rate data of hydro-

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of α and β -naphthyl phosphates at constant ionic strength at 80°.

α -naphthyl O
 β -naphthyl x.

lysis (Figure 1) indicates that

- neutral species is reactive as lines do not pass through origin⁹,
- acid catalyzed hydrolysis via conjugate acid species is present,
- neutral rate is subject to ionic acceleration, as straight lines have different intercepts on rate axis,
- the rates of hydrolysis at 7 μ in α -naphthyl and 6, 7 μ in β -naphthyl phosphate decrease with increase in acid concentration.

The total rate of reaction at any acidity can be represented by the equation,¹⁰

$$k_e = k_{H_0} \exp. bH^+\mu + k_{N_0} \exp. bN\mu.$$

where k_e , k_{H_0} , k_{N_0} , b and μ are observed rates, specific acid catalyzed rate, specific neutral rate at zero ionic strength, a constant and ionic strength respectively. Acid catalyzed and neutral rates are then calculated using following equations and results are summarized in Table 1 :

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha\text{-naphthyl phosphate acid rate} \\ 7 + \log K_A = 3.75 - 0.217\mu H^+ \\ \text{neutral rate } 7 + \log K_N = 3.05 + 0.15 \mu \\ \beta\text{-naphthyl phosphate acid rate} \\ 7 + \log K_A = 3.45 - 0.227\mu H^+ \\ \text{neutral rate } 7 + \log K_N = 2.85 + 0.207 \mu \end{aligned}$$

The sum of acid and neutral rates agrees well upto 5M perchloric acid as in *p*-chloro and *p*-bromo phenyl phosphates², however, such separation of rates was not possible in *p*-nitro and *p*-acetyl phenyl phosphates due to complicated salt effect data.¹ The effectiveness of acid catalysis thus follows the order $\text{NO}_2 > \text{CH}_3\text{CO} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \alpha\text{-naphthyl} > \beta\text{-naphthyl}$.

A change-over from water to water-dioxan mixtures brings about a decrease in rates (Table 1), which implies a more polar nature of transition state than initial state.¹¹ The ratio $\text{KD}_2\text{O}/\text{KH}_2\text{O}$ for β -naphthyl phosphate at 4M perchloric acid is 0.7, which shows a slow proton transfer^{8,12}. The values of Arrhenius parameters also favour the bimolecular nature of the reaction.¹³ Plots of $\log k + H_0$ against $\log a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ gave values of Bunnett parameters as 5.3 and 5.6 for α and β -naphthyl phosphates respectively. This suggests a slow proton transfer with a nucleophilic attack of water molecule¹⁴.

Phenyl phosphate undergoes hydrolysis via its neutral species¹⁵ with phosphorus-oxygen bond fission and same has been presumed for *p*-nitro, *p*-tolyl¹, *p*-chloro and *p*-bromo² phenyl phosphates. Similarly on the basis of comparative rate data with other phosphate esters,^{2,9} the neutral and acid catalyzed hydrolysis of α - and β -naphthyl phosphates can be presumed to take place with phosphorus-oxygen bond fission and following mechanism can be formulated for acid catalyzed and neutral hydrolysis as :

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